

Identifying Fraudulent Behaviour in Student Communications During Online Multiple – Choice Assessments

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KEYWORDS

Online Evaluation Fraud,
Communication Probability
Analysis,
MCQ Exam Integrity,
Collusion Detection Model,
Statistical Fraud Assessment

ABSTRACT

Online evaluation systems, pervasive nowadays, are known to be susceptible to higher fraud risks. This work proposes a novel and robust method to detect potential fraud acts in online multiple-choice question (MCQ) exams. For the first time, the communication probability between the examinees is statistically assessed based on the concordance of responses and answer time against null expectations and is subsequently used to identify potential fraud behavior. The model is sensitive to the direction of communication acts, distinguishing content consumption from production, as well as multwise communication channels. Online remote tests from engineering courses at Tecnico Lisboa are used as a case study. We show that the cumulative contribution of concordant responses between students, when recurrent, offers a way of signaling fraud behavior. Separating content production from consumption reveals the underlying student role played in potential fraud acts. Collusion behavior is assessed against null models of fraud and conformity, and therefore being statistically framed and offering a solid criterion to guide tutors in ascertaining fraud and discouraging communication.

1. INTRODUCTION

OVER the last decade, alongside the developments in technology came, for students, the possibility to enroll in a wide variety of online courses and, in some colleges, to choose between the traditional face-to-face classes and the computer-based classes. Online courses attained

their popularity by providing students the flexibility to work in a self-paced manner and reduce attendance costs . University administrators are motivated to present online content and assessments to ensure a broader student reach . The COVID-19 pandemic converted this possibility into a necessity . However,

with the remote way of teaching comes the challenge of unsupervised online testing, shown to yield a higher possibility of fraud, challenging the fair principle of evaluation. We define fraud as all forms of illegitimate activities that are aimed at increasing one's assessment performance. These activities include using unauthorized materials, copying, collusion among examinees, acquisition of test content (also termed pre knowledge), impersonation, or external assistance from someone who is not taking the test. In this study, the focus is on collusion among examinees, the arguably most common form of online cheating in multiple choice question (MCQ) exams performed at individual homes. Several statistics have been proposed to assess collusion ranging from item response theory to the analysis of response times. Nevertheless, the existing methods generally suffer from three major drawbacks: 1) Assume fixed question orders and reversible answering; 2) Neglect the distinguished roles and multi wise cumulative effects from inadvertent content sharing exerted in unauthorized communication platforms; 3) Do not reliably test the deviation of the acquired behavioral statistics against plausible expectations.

As the first comprehensive effort to address these limitations, this work establishes a novel method to detect potential fraud acts based on time stamped answer records from online quizzes with shuffled questions, capturing potential multi wise acts of information exchange by examinees taking the test at the same time. In the context of multiple choice online test environments, this is an increasing need as fraud can be attained by either direct in-room communication or via instant messaging applications, for instance, WhatsApp and Messenger, as electronic communication is becoming more pervasive worldwide with the spread of the Internet. As such, handling collusion, irrespective of the communication method, is the pivotal requirement tackled in this study. In this context, the following major questions arise: Is it possible to identify collusion fraud taking into consideration both the selected options and their timestamps? How can collusion candidates be statistically tested to minimize false discoveries? Can we further inquire into the nature of inadvertent communication between students, including its directionality (inadvertent content sharing and/or consumption) and cardinality (number of involved students)? This work offers a comprehensive discussion

of these research questions. To this end, we propose a disruptive methodology to assess fraud communication which starts from a pre analysis of the data to accommodate distinct patterns of fraudulent behavior. The methodology sustains itself in the following four major principles:

- 1) A statistical frame to assess the probability of pairwise student communication considering: a) matched answers; b) choice probability; c) response times (directionality); and d) recurrence of suspicious behavior;
- 2) a network representation of potential communication acts grounded on the previous probabilistic stance, allowing the assessment of directional multi wise communication acts in a multiple choice online test;
- 3) Null models of compliance and fraud from the principled understanding of inadvertent communication to test collusion dynamics and identify them with strict guarantees of statistical significance;
- 4) Scoring, clustering, and visualization principles to facilitate the understanding of inadvertent communication pathways and promote the action ability of recommendations, supporting the course's tutor with subsequent inquiry acts and advertence initiatives.

As a case study, we consider online remote tests performed on the Quizzes Tutor's platform, developed at Técnico Lisboa. Students receive the questions in different orders (shuffling) and cannot return to a question they have already answered or skipped. There is limited monitoring capacity of the students' behavior. Periodic quizzes from software architecture (SA) course are used to validate the proposal. The remainder work structure is organized as follows. Section II introduces essential background. Section III discusses relevant work. Section IV introduces the target fraud detection model. In Section V, null models of student behavior are specified to assess differences between compliant and fraudulent behavior. Section VI proposes a methodology to detect potential fraud acts against behavioral expectations and find multi wise communication channels. Section VII discusses the acquired results, comparing the target model against existing scores. Deployment notes are discussed in Section VIII. Concluding marks are finally provided.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

As precedent research shows, students cheat for numerous reasons, which are not strictly associated with

online testing [22], [23]. These reasons may include low grades and ineffective study strategies; poor time management skills; personal values and views which relate to achievement, fear of punishment, class attendance, and peer pressure; extrinsic versus intrinsic motivations to learn; and age [10]. Ladyshevsky [10] observed that some student profiles will attempt to cheat regardless of the mode of instruction. Although earlier studies yield no conclusive evidence that remote online assessments increase cheating likelihood [24], [25], recent results show that there is a significant increase in dishonest behaviors in remote assessments [11], [23]. Several statistics, grounded on item response theory and the analysis of response times, have been proposed to detect unexpected gain scores, collusion, pre-knowledge, and other abnormal behaviors [15], [26], including I^*z [27], HT [17], L_s [18], S [20], erasure index [19], and cumulative distribution indices [16], each with varying degrees of success [18], [28]. Ranger et al. [13] compared several cheating indicators and were unable to find indicators that could discriminate preknowledge from test collusion. Withal, the authors found out that indicators based on response times were pivotal to decrease fraud intentions and further recommend avoiding grading on a curve to decrease cheating behaviors motivated by peer competition. Tiong and Lee [33] developed an e-cheating intelligence agent for online assessments that is further able to access the Internet Protocol (IP) of the students, issuing alerts when students changed their device or initial location. The agent is capable of preventive behaviors as it is dynamically able to reassign questions in instances where abnormal behavior is detected. One of the challenges of working with statistical models of fraud is the inherent difficulty of identifying the cut-off values that separate normal from atypical response profiles. Man et al. [26] placed a supervised stance on fraud detection to tackle this challenge. Using predictive learning, the authors were able to compare the discriminative power of the statistics using the collected fraud evidence and further conclude that the use of predictive models able to combine multiple sources of information can lead to a higher detection rate over traditional item response and response time methods. Alexandron et al. [34] proposed a semisupervised anomaly detection approach, trained on a known set of cheaters, to detect fraud. The approach is shown to be capable of

generalizing well toward cheaters with distinct behaviors. A new time-based statistic—the fraction of items that were solved correctly in significantly lower time than the average time of correct responses on those items—is proposed to assess aberrant behaviors. Despite the relevance of the placed (semi)supervised stances, their transfer and deployment across different courses and cultures are arguably limited as it requires the presence of expressive forms of cheating behavior from different contexts. The presence of ground truth to develop and assess academic dishonesty is a well-recognized difficulty [15]. Man et al. [26] considered a case study where students had the opportunity to illegally steal exam content before assessment. Complementary cheating behavior during the exam was further flagged via postinvestigation clearance. To validate fraud detection in mixed face-in-face and online settings, Balderas et al. [30] considered the differential analysis of grades between settings to validate findings. Understandably, these assumptions disregard the fact that changes in academic performance can be undertaken with integrity and are further restricted to mixed evaluations in the context of a course or academic path. Bilen and Matros [32] and Tiong and Lee [33] validated fraud models by predefining cheating as the ability to quickly answer difficult questions. Although useful, these labeling assumptions are arguably biased and limited to specific forms of fraud and dependent on parameterizable cut-off thresholds that assume the homogeneity of student profiles.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

As precedent research shows, students cheat for numerous reasons, which are not strictly associated with online testing [22], [23]. These reasons may include low grades and ineffective study strategies; poor time management skills; personal values and views which relate to achievement, fear of punishment, class attendance, and peer pressure; extrinsic versus intrinsic motivations to learn; and age [10]. Ladyshevsky [10] observed that some student profiles will attempt to cheat regardless of the mode of instruction. Although earlier studies yield no conclusive evidence that remote online assessments increase cheating likelihood [24], [25], recent results show that there is a significant increase in dishonest behaviors in remote assessments [11], [23]. Several statistics, grounded on item response theory

and the analysis of response times, have been proposed to detect unexpected gain scores, collusion, pre-knowledge, and other abnormal behaviors [15], [26], including $l * z$ [27], HT [17], Ls [18], S [20], erasure index [19], and cumulative distribution indices [16], each with varying degrees of success [18], [28]. Ranger et al. [13] compared several cheating indicators and were unable to find indicators that could discriminate pre-knowledge from test collusion. Withal, the authors found out that indicators based on response times were capable to detect pre-knowledge but not test collusion, and indicators based on the response revisions were capable to detect test collusion but lack the power to detect pre-knowledge of the various cheating indicators purposed in the recent Ranger et al. study [13], we highlight three statistics based on the selected responses—U1, U3, and CS—and four which are based on the editions/revisions to a given response—N1, NC1, N2, and NC2. The indicators based on the selected responses constitute the most basic way to analyze an examinee's performance since they solely require that, for each question, the option chosen by each student is saved, while the indicators based on the response's revisions are of particular interest as capable of detecting test collusion. In our work, each student receives the questions that compose a quiz in distinct order, with shuffled possible options, and is further prevented from going back and editing responses to previous questions. As such, collusion statistics based on response revisions are insufficient. In addition, most of the previous statistics, including those in [13], do not consider the concordance of responses between students against chance agreements, which is a normal condition for communication attempts within the class. Furthermore, some of the existing indicators neglect the rich temporal frame at which responses are provided, preventing the possibility to assess the significance and directionality of potential copy acts between students.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We propose a disruptive methodology to assess fraud communication which starts from a pre analysis of the data to accommodate distinct patterns of fraudulent behavior. The methodology sustains itself in the following four major principles:

1) A statistical frame to assess the probability of pairwise student communication considering: a)

matched answers; b) choice probability; c) response times (directionality); and d) recurrence of suspicious behavior;

2) A network representation of potential communication acts grounded on the previous probabilistic stance, allowing the assessment of directional multiwise communication acts in a multiple choice online test;

3) Null models of compliance and fraud from the principled understanding of inadvertent communication to test collusion dynamics and identify them with strict guarantees of statistical significance;

4) Scoring, clustering, and visualization principles to facilitate the understanding of inadvertent communication pathways and promote the action ability of recommendations, supporting the course's tutor with subsequent inquiry acts and advertence initiatives.

5. ALGORITHM

Input:

- responses[]: A list of student responses to each question.
- timestamps[]: The time taken by each student to answer each question.
- students[]: A list of students participating in the exam.
- num_questions: Total number of questions in the exam.
- threshold_concordance: A predefined threshold for detecting unusual response similarity.
- threshold_time: A predefined threshold for detecting suspiciously short or synchronized answer times.

Output:

- A list of students flagged for potential fraud.

Step 1: Preprocess Data

1. **Normalize timestamps** to ensure consistent time units.
2. **Convert responses** into a matrix $R[\text{students}][\text{questions}]$, where each entry represents a student's response.

Step 2: Compute Concordance Score

3. For each pair of students (S_1, S_2): Compute **response concordance**:

$$C(S1, S2) = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^{num_questions} I(R[S1, q] = R[S2, q])}{num_questions}$$

where I(condition) is 1 if true, 0 otherwise.

- If $C(S1, S2) > threshold_concordance$, mark them as *highly similar*.

Step 3: Analyze Answer Timing

4. For each pair of students (S1, S2):

Computetime similarity score:

$$T(S1, S2) = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^{num_questions} I(|time[S1, q] - time[S2, q]| < threshold_time)}{num_questions}$$

- If $T(S1, S2) > threshold_time$, mark them as *suspiciously synchronized*.

Step 4: Identify Potential Fraud

5. **Flag students** where both conditions hold:
 - If $C(S1, S2) > threshold_concordance$ **and** $T(S1, S2) > threshold_time$, label (S1, S2) as a *potential fraudulent pair*.
6. **Analyze direction of communication:**
 - Identify **content producers** (students who answered first).
 - Identify **content consumers** (students who answered later with high concordance).

Step 5: Statistical Validation Against Null Model

7. Generate a **null model** by simulating random responses and random timestamps.
8. Compare observed fraud scores (C and T) against the null model to determine statistical significance.
9. If fraud likelihood exceeds a confidence threshold (e.g., $p < 0.05$), classify students as potential cheaters.

Step 6: Output and Actions

10. Generate a **report** listing flagged students, their suspected partners, and fraud likelihood.
11. Provide **recommendations** to tutors for manual review and further action.

Complexity Analysis

- Concordance and timing checks run in $O(n^2 * num_questions)$, where n is the number of

students.

- Can be optimized using **hashing techniques** or **machine learning models** for anomaly detection.

6. RESULTS

6.1 Output Screens

Fig 6.1 User Login Page

In above screen shows the Login page of the User.

Fig 6.2 User Registration Page

In above screen shows the User Registration page

Fig 6.3 Admin Login

In above screen shows Admin Login.

Fig 6.4 Admin Home Page

In above screen shows the Admin Home Page.

Fig 6.5 Detecting Fraudulent student Communication

In above screen shows the Detecting Fraudulent student Communication.

7. CONCLUSION

This work introduced a novel methodology to assess likely fraud communication acts in remote online MCQ exams based on the concordance of responses and answer times. Null models are produced to understand regular versus fraud dynamics and to identify collusion with strict guarantees of statistical significance. Complementarily, clustering algorithms are applied to unravel communication channels between students.

Considering matched answers, choice probability, response times (directionality), and recurrence, we show that it is possible to create a network of potential communication acts between students. Having constructed the network for null models representing fraudulent and honest behavior, we obtain insights into how to separate spurious communication from the actual interchange of information.

Finally, employing these insights on the real data and making use of scoring techniques, we are able to categorize each student with respect to their fraud likelihood and thus understand inadvertent communication pathways and promote the action ability of recommendations, supporting the course's tutor with the subsequent inquiry or advertence initiatives.

The application of the proposed principles in the context of the SA course reveals students with higher fraud likelihood, already showing to be a solid criterion to guide tutors in ascertaining collusion and discouraging communication. In this work, fraudulent behavior analysis was primarily pursued in the context of a single quiz. However, if deviant behavior is detected in more than one quiz, the chances of fraudulent behavior considerably increase. In this context, binomial testing can be straightforwardly applied to identify the probability of observing a given number of potential fraud acts.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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